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Annotatsiya: in this thesis, the online participation of the translator in the court process, the platforms, applications and programs on which the translator performs the translation work, the doctrines of the translator's work are highlighted, and the useful aspects of chatGPT, which is entering the work of the translator today, are considered. In addition, in order to accelerate the online participation of the translator, procedural legal documents were analyzed and suggestions and recommendations were made for improvement.

Kalit so'zlar: interpreter, application, platform, program, online, chatgpt, court, process.

Enter

Digitization of the work of a translator, one of the persons who help in the implementation of justice, is important in the era of artificial intelligence. The relevant code, laws and even the plenary decision guarantee the right to use the services of an interpreter for persons who do not know the language of economic court proceedings. Even when the court session is held in the video conference mode, the participants of the court proceedings who do not know the language in the court are guaranteed the right to participate in the courts with the help of an interpreter and to speak in their native language[1]. Also, the rights and obligations are explained, and a receipt is received and sent to the court hearing

the case. If the translator does not come, or if he wants to present additional evidence, or if it is not possible to set up a video conference (in the case of technical malfunctions, as well as interruptions in the supply of electricity), the cases are postponed to the next one. When the court session is adjourned for this reason, the court considering the case appoints an IT officer of the court who will assist in holding a court session in videoconference mode through another means of communication, and this employee, in turn, will assist the participants in the proceedings who came to the court session (interpreter, witness, specialist and expert) is to be notified by receipt about the date and time of the new court session. Several platforms, applications and other programs are used in foreign countries to ensure the remote participation of translators in court. For example, Kudo is a cloud-based platform for multilingual meetings and events. It provides remote simultaneous translation that allows translators to work from anywhere in the world. It is commonly used for court proceedings, conferences, webinars and virtual events[2]. The platform transmits real-time human-language translation by translators to participants' smartphones and computers, so anyone can join in any language of their choice from anywhere. Up to 32 languages can be supported per meeting. Kudo allows customers to bring their own interpreters to the platform or book professional interpreters through the Kudo Interpreter Marketplace.

In addition, the remote platforms ZipDX and Boostlingo are also important platforms for translators and courts. They allow translators to join virtual meetings and provide real-time translation services. The Boostlingo platform uses both translation and sign translation at the same time, managing translators, providing virtual simultaneous or consecutive translation.

ChatGPT is a powerful language model that has the ability to perform natural language translation. Its capabilities are based on its ability to understand and generate text in multiple languages, which allows it to accurately recognize and

translate idioms, colloquialisms, and even dialects. ChatGPT is a powerful language model that is trained on a massive amount of text data, giving it the ability to understand and generate human language[3]. One of the most impressive capabilities of ChatGPT is its ability to adapt to different dialects and colloquialisms. Dialects and colloquialisms refer to variations of a language that are specific to a particular location or group of people. These variations can include different pronunciations, grammar, vocabulary, and idioms. Traditional machine translation methods often struggle with dialects and colloquialisms, resulting in translations that are less than perfect.

The possibilities for ChatGPT in language translation are endless. Its ability to adapt to different dialects and colloquialisms, take context into account, and handle multiple languages simultaneously makes it a powerful tool for breaking down language barriers and facilitating communication in multicultural environments. Additionally, its potential in helping non-native speakers improve their language skills and its integration with other systems such as chatbots, makes it a valuable tool for companies operating in a global market and for people trying to communicate with people who speak different languages.

Another must-have platform (app) for translators in the US is Languageline[4]. This involves finding and establishing a telephone connection with a qualified interpreter for interpreting over the phone or computer, and arranging to pay the interpreter for the service. On this "Languageline" platform, it is determined and reflected that the translators have a certificate or other qualification. In court, telephone interpreting services are provided in formal court settings and for out-of-court interviews lasting from a few minutes to several hours. Languageline Services (LLS) provides translation services to clients in more than 140 languages. The service works 24 hours a day. In most cases (about 98 percent), the connection is established within a minute of receiving a service request. The fee for the translator is the first connection fee and the minimum

monthly fee is determined. The recipient of the interpreter service will be provided with an ID number and a personal access code. In addition, based on "Closed Captioning and Transcription", during online translation[5], for the deaf and hard of hearing and for those who prefer written transcription, converting audio to written text and real-time text at the bottom of the screen and any sound, voice and otherwise appear.

These programs, programs and applications are useful for translator and translation activities. In it, it is highly appreciated that the implementation of the translation, the translation being clear and concise, finding and engaging interpreters, providing remote participation, real-time translation and providing surd-ova subtitling services for the deaf-mute are highly appreciated. .

Conclusion

Based on the above, firstly the creation of the "e-translator.uz" website and application, and the list of translators, surnames, first names, surnames, translation languages, seniority, sign language translators, a warning about criminal liability through an online receipt, and a certificate check through this site, the level of language translation is determined, translation prices are quoted, the level of security is determined. Through the application, online translation is performed in real time.

Secondly, active implementation of ChatGPT for cooperation between interpreters and courts in the courts of Uzbekistan and as a result will save time and money in the courts.

List of used literature

1 <https://lex.uz/docs/-2534033>

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